

Interview with Japanese Animator and Director Masahiro Emoto at FicZone 2024

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Masahiro Emoto is a Japanese artist with several decades of experience in the animation industry. Highly versatile, he has worked in roles ranging from in-betweener to designer, character designer, animation director, and director, contributing to renowned studios such as Madhouse, Production I.G, WIT Studio, Studio Pierrot, and Bones, among many others, as well as engaging in independent projects.

You may recall some of the projects he has been involved in, including the iconic *Ghost in the Shell* (1995, directed by Mamoru Oshii), and anime series such as *Shingeki no Kyojin*, *Tokyo Revengers*, *Bleach*, *Samurai Champloo*, and the current *Samurai X (Rurōni Kenshin, 2023)*, on which he was still working at the time of this interview. He has also contributed to video games such as *Lunar-2: Eternal Blue* (Sega Saturn, 1994) and *JoJo's Bizarre Adventure: All-Star Battle* (2013).

Emoto has applied his skills to projects like the anime adaptation of *Blade* (2011) and *Animatrix* (2003), and he is enthusiastic about robotics and AI, contributing visually and in design to contemporary projects such as GROOVE-X's LOVOT.

Interview with Masahiro Emoto

Cool Japan: Good morning, Mr Emoto. To begin with, could you tell us about your background? Did you always want to dedicate yourself to art? Is drawing your favourite activity?

Masahiro Emoto: Good morning, thank you. I didn't attend university, though I did complete high school. Afterwards, I thought I might work in animation, as I really enjoy drawing. I started drawing, and with those drawings I went to Tokyo, gradually entering the animation industry.

Regarding your other questions... now that I am in Granada... what I enjoy is seeing people, meeting people. Not so much landscapes, but people, diverse individuals. That is what interests me the most right now.

Cool Japan: How did you begin in the animation industry? Can you tell us about your early career?

Masahiro Emoto: Starting in animation wasn't too difficult for me. I don't believe I draw better than anyone else. What I think is that, perhaps by working a lot, slowly, both my character and technique have improved.

Cool Japan: You've worked on productions well known internationally, such as *Ghost in the Shell*, *Jin-Roh*, the 2001 *Cowboy Bebop* film, or *Samurai Champloo*. How do you feel about the tremendous impact of these projects, not just in Japan but internationally?

Masahiro Emoto: Everyone involved in these works... none of us expected them to become so relevant and well-known worldwide. The first reaction was always something like, "What? Really? Has this become so famous?" including myself. It is surprising.

For example, take *Samurai Champloo*, which became very popular, and it was interesting and striking, not only for Japanese audiences but globally. I did expect something like that could happen.

However, in the case of *Tokyo Revengers*, on the other hand, I didn't imagine it would be so popular outside Japan... I thought it wasn't anything "new", and there are no samurais... and I wondered, "Why is this happening?"

Cool Japan: Projects like *Ghost in the Shell* and studios like Production I.G or Tezuka Productions were pioneers in adopting digital techniques and their subsequent industry-wide implementation. What has this transition from analogue to digital meant for you?

Masahiro Emoto: That's a very difficult question... [Thoughtful] For example, painting by hand used to take much longer. When working with colours, you had to wait for them to dry. With digital art, once you have a drawing and put it on the computer, you can paint directly, without waiting for the colours to dry. This saves a lot of time.

When using analogue techniques, for a single background, I sometimes had to send it abroad, even to China or Korea, to be painted, and then wait to receive it finished. With the computer, you spend much less time.

Since I started working in analogue and by hand, using digital techniques takes me longer than if I worked natively in digital. However, younger artists, twenty years old or younger, have started drawing directly in digital. For them, it is much easier. For me, it's a little different.

Especially for me, it's very useful, as I love travelling and visiting other places and countries. For example, next week, I have to work, and I can do it almost as if I were in Tokyo. That is much better for me.

Emoto demonstrates his command of the digital world, showing anime enthusiasts at FicZone 2024 how he creates a live portrait of an attendee. He paused at times to explain the steps in an engaging way, allowing visitors to see how the portrait was made.

Cool Japan: What was your involvement with *Shingeki no Kyojin*?

Masahiro Emoto: As far as I remember, when I was involved with *Shingeki no Kyojin*, I was also working on the *Jojo's All-Star Battle* video game. At that time, I was very busy, and the anime's director, who is a friend of mine, asked me to help with the ending of the series' second season and with a few illustrations for the project. However, I didn't have a major role in that project because I already had a heavy workload at the time.

Cool Japan: You have an extensive career in the anime industry, having been an in-betweener, key animator, character designer, storyboard artist, animation director, and director. Which of these roles has contributed the most to you artistically and professionally?

Masahiro Emoto: What happens to me, for example, when I work as an animator is that I think... "Next time, I'll do something different"; and when I work as a director, I think... "Next time, I'll try another approach." I'm always thinking about pushing further.

Right now, I work as a director and animation director, and I love it.

Cool Japan: You have also worked on projects with a distinctly Western character, such as *Animatrix*, and Japanese versions of *Blade* and *Iron Man*, both highly respected in the West. What can you tell us about these experiences?

Masahiro Emoto: Well, even though they are based on American comics, the techniques we use are Japanese, the visual style is Japanese, and we do them in Japan... so, for me, there was no real difference.

Cool Japan: Last year, you faced the challenge of working on *Rurōni Kenshin*, a franchise well-known in Europe, with a previous adaptation of the character *Kenshin Himura* by Watsuki from 1996, which had its own style. How did you and your team approach this challenge?

Masahiro Emoto: One of our main concerns at the studio was, since there was already a famous previous adaptation, not to fall short of the earlier series, while trying to create something new at the same time. Another key element was to consider the strengths of the previous adaptation, in order to highlight them in a more modern version of the story. These were the main points we focused on.

Cool Japan: You have worked with renowned directors like Shin'Ichiro Watanabe and Mamoru Oshii. Is there a specific director you would like to work with, or someone you would like to collaborate with again?

Masahiro Emoto: The director I respect and admire the most is Shigeru Yamazaki [a veteran artist who has worked on well-known animes such as *Street Fighter II V*, *Macross*, and *Record of Lodoss War*]. Because I respect and admire his work so much, I don't wish to work with him at the moment.

Cool Japan: You have even been involved in projects related to video games, such as *Jojo's Bizarre Adventure: All-Star Battle*, *Lunar 2*, and the *Ghost in the Shell* PlayStation project. What differences or challenges do you find when working for a video game?

Masahiro Emoto: The first difference is, for example, 3D animation, which is more common in video games. My work for a video game takes much less time than on an anime or animated film, but you spend more time with the character you are helping to create.

In a video game, the main difference is that you are the protagonist, you control the character... but these are no longer drawings, although I still work on these characters. In an animated series, the character moves from here to there, and everything must be done by hand. It's not the same. The difference isn't huge, but it isn't the same as working on an animated series.

Ken Yamaya (interpreter): In video games, there are many more effects and short animations. I would like to know if there is a big difference compared to animations in anime series or animated films.

Masahiro Emoto: That's right. Unlike in animated series, unless you plan from the start to do something in 3D or have scenes you want to make in 3D even if the series is 2D, generally everything is drawn, frame by frame, even digitally. You have to consider not just the design of a character or element, but the movement it will make, and you have to draw everything.

In video games, it works differently: you start by designing the character and then modelling it in 3D, because you know it will be like that, and then you add effects and animations afterwards.

Cool Japan: Regarding the *Jojo's Bizarre Adventure: All-Star Battle* video game, what was your role?

Masahiro Emoto: I was involved in both *All-Star Battle* (2013) and the follow-up, *Eyes of Heaven* (2015), and I basically handled character design. [Following this link, an illustration of Josuke Higashikata, a character from *Jojo's Bizarre Adventure* created by Hirohiko Araki, drawn by Emoto himself]

If there's something characteristic about *Jojo's*, it's that there are many important characters, and I designed them all for the game. In *All-Star Battle*, I also created some images that appear in story mode, to set the scene for certain characters after battles. I don't remember all the details, but I believe some of these illustrations appear in various parts of the game.

Throughout the creation process of these video games, I usually did the designs, then passed them to the developers [in this case, CyberConnect2] and the studio would give suggestions about what changes to make to a character, or if it resembled the manga character enough. I applied their suggestions and modified the designs accordingly. At the beginning of the process, when the first animations and movements were made, they often asked for my opinion, and I gave my vision of how it should look.

Cool Japan: Which project have you enjoyed the most, and which was the most challenging?

Masahiro Emoto: The one I enjoyed the most was *Yamadeloid*, which is probably available on YouTube and other platforms, and I encourage you to watch it. The most challenging projects... There are two: *Redline* [2009], which was a very famous film, and *Sennen Joyū* [*Millennium Actress*].

Cool Japan: We were going to ask you about one of these projects. Along with Takashi Horiuchi, you created the short animation *Yamadeloid*. What did this project mean to you?

Masahiro Emoto: Hideaki Anno, the director of *Evangelion*, liked it very much. If I spoke about *Yamadeloid* in depth... there's so much I could tell you, but that's for another time. I can say that I put my whole being into this project, and afterwards, I spent some time without working in animation or anything similar, because I needed a break. [In the following link, you will find *Yamadeloid*, in which Masahiro Emoto participated]

Cool Japan: What can you tell us about your work on AI projects such as LOVOT and other robots capable of interpreting and mimicking human emotions? Are you also passionate about robotics? We think this is reflected in *Yamadeloid!* The real world is increasingly resembling video games by your compatriot Yokō Tarō (*NieR*), with thinking, almost human robots.

Masahiro Emoto: Yes! I am passionate about robots! I am currently working both as an animator and developing artificial intelligence. In the projects I'm involved with, such as LOVOT, they are basically “pet” robots, designed to form bonds of friendship and affection with humans.

[Thoughtful] In the future, I think many types of AI and robots will be developed, with a significant societal impact. This is exciting, but we must carefully consider their development and the qualities they will possess, as it can be both beneficial and potentially harmful.

Cool Japan: In the 1990s and 2000s, there was the first anime revolution with digitalisation —beginning with *Love Hina* and films like *Princess Mononoke* or *Blood: The Last Vampire*— and a second wave with 3D integration in many anime, though 3D was already used in classics like *Golgo 13* in the 1980s. Do you think AI will also impact anime?

Masahiro Emoto: I am already paying attention to all this. It's like what I said before about young artists who started drawing directly with digital tools. What happens will depend on how AI evolves in the future. Many artists are concerned, but I believe that anything handcrafted will always have more value than something created entirely artificially.

Cool Japan: Thank you very much, Mr Emoto!

Masahiro Emoto: ¡Gracias! (Thank you!) [He said this in Spanish.]

Promotional image of LOVOT, shown alongside a human being.

Acknowledgements

Of course, we would not want to conclude without expressing our gratitude to the artist himself, Masahiro Emoto, who granted us one of the most special interviews we have ever conducted, and which required the participation of several Japanese collaborators, including him. He made a notable impression on Granada’s local businesses —such as the renowned restaurant Bodega Casa Castañeda— and was interviewed by various local media outlets. Always carrying his drawing tools, whether strolling through Granada or creating portraits and landscapes around the city.

We also extend our thanks to the CrossOver association, the FicZone staff—including the press team and volunteers— and to the event director, Nacho Cabrero, for consistently supporting events that welcome guests like Masahiro Emoto, and for allowing us to interview him. Once again, congratulations on an event that breaks records every year.

We must also thank the Yamaya family, both Michie and her son Ken, who have collaborated with us flawlessly on previous occasions and without whom this interview would have been impossible. The owners of Kurama Sushi & Poke, a Japanese restaurant in Granada, Javier and Catalina, also deserve recognition here, as they kindly offered their premises for some of the questions posed to Emoto, and assisted us during the subsequent meeting in the city. Catalina prepared sushi that made our interviewee feel at home, while Javier provided drinks that impressed everyone. Finally, we wish to extend our thanks to the Japanese-born artist Wakana Sakamoto, based in Granada, who also assisted our colleague as an interpreter with Mr Emoto.

Masahiro Emoto at Kurama Sushi & Poke restaurant, alongside Wakana Sakamoto, Michie Yamaya, Andrés Domenech Alcaide, and Catalina López Sako.

Masahiro Emoto met with anime and video game enthusiasts at FicZone—the cover photograph of this interview comes from this very event— and also held signing sessions, some accompanied by true works of art, which he spent several minutes creating for each person, something he did with pleasure.

It was during one of these encounters that we saw him drawing live for the first time, with attendees able to pose as models for a few minutes. Emoto also gave a talk at the Granada Chamber of Commerce on artificial intelligence and its applications for businesses on 5 April. [At this link, you can see how Emoto shared on his social media the portrait he made of a young attendee at his meeting with anime fans.]

If we were to take away one thing about Mr Emoto, it is his great humility and genuine passion for art. Despite his experience and artistic talent, he never seems to lose the drive to improve, and he always strives for more. He exudes youthfulness and cheerfulness, remains calm and respectful at all times, is curious to learn new things, meet new people, and gives helpful advice when asked, always politely. He not only remembers the many projects he has worked on, but also admires the original works he has adapted and the artists behind them. He produces drawings of all kinds—characters, landscapes, portraits, fanarts—which can be publicly seen on his social media.

What kept him busy in our country was not only his outstanding participation at FicZone, but also other events in cities such as Málaga. He took the opportunity to explore Spain from end to end, visiting several autonomous communities along the way—he is a true explorer, loving to walk, discover new places, try new routes—and never once put down his drawing tools or stopped working. Whenever he saw something interesting to draw, he would put on his glasses and get to work!

He was so kind as to show interest in the training and experience of our colleague, Andrés, who conducted the interview for CoolJapan.es, and they met again before Emoto left Granada. Masahiro Emoto decided to create not one, but two portraits of our colleague Andrés, which he presented as gifts.

Portraits of Andrés Domenech Alcaide created by Masahiro Emoto in April 2024

Sources

- **Texts consulted from:** FicZone 2024 official website, MyAnimeList, LOVOT official website | **Interview conducted by:** Andrés Domenech Alcaide [CoolJapan.es] | **Interview interpreted by:** Michie Yamaya, Ken Yamaya, Wakana Sakamoto

- **Images sourced from:** FicZone 2024 official website, LOVOT official website|
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- *Originally published on CoolJapan.es on 13 July 2024 —Entrevista a Masahiro Emoto en FicZone 2024—*
- *This version is a faithful translation into English by Andrés Domenech Alcaide*